

2025

BBNJ

SYMPOSIUM

REPORT

18-19 February 2025

Symposium Organisers

CIL

CENTRE FOR INTERNATIONAL LAW
National University of Singapore

MINISTRY OF
FOREIGN AFFAIRS
SINGAPORE

in collaboration with

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Acronyms

ABMTs	Area-Based Management Tools
ABNJ	Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction
ABS	Access and Benefit-Sharing
APEI	Areas of Particular Environmental Interest
BBNJ	Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CBTMT	Capacity-Building and Transfer of Marine Technology
CHM	Clearing House Mechanism
DOALOS	Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea, Office of Legal Affairs, UN
DSI	Digital Sequence Information
CIL-NUS	Centre for International Law, National University of Singapore
COP	Conference of the Parties
EBSA	Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Area
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization (of the UN)
GEF	Global Environment Facility
ICC	Implementation and Compliance Committee
IFBs	Instruments, Frameworks and Bodies
IGO	Intergovernmental Organisation
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IPLC	Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities
ISA	International Seabed Authority
MGR	Marine Genetic Resources
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
PSSA	Particularly Sensitive Sea Area
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisation
STB	Scientific and Technical Body
UNCLOS	UN Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNFCCC	UN Framework Convention on Climate Change
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem

Meeting Summary

The BBNJ Symposium 2025 featured a comprehensive agenda over two days, beginning with a welcome address and a keynote speech, and including six panel discussions that addressed the BBNJ Agreement’s ratification, implementation, and broader implications for ocean governance. Alongside these panels, the symposium included a fireside chat with the BBNJ Preparatory Commission co-chairs and a research roundtable that discussed the role and management of science and diverse knowledge systems as the treaty moves towards entry into force. The symposium was designed to foster progress towards the Agreement's early entry into force by engaging a diverse range of perspectives from government, civil society, and the research community, particularly drawing insights from the Asia-Pacific region. Discussions also previewed the ongoing and future work of the BBNJ Preparatory Commission.

The following sections of this report capture key take-away messages from each session of the Symposium, based on the minutes taken by the Symposium rapporteurs.

The BBNJ Agreement demonstrated the success of multilateralism and collective decision-making in marine protection.

The BBNJ Symposium 2025 opened with insightful addresses by Ambassador-at-Large Professor Tommy Koh and Singapore's Minister for Foreign Affairs, Dr Vivian Balakrishnan. Both speakers underscored the importance of international cooperation and the adherence to the rule of law in oceans affairs, including marine conservation and biodiversity. Ambassador Koh detailed the significance of the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), highlighting its adaptability over 40 years through implementing agreements such as the BBNJ Agreement. Minister Balakrishnan emphasised the BBNJ Agreement's critical role in ensuring the fair and equitable use of marine resources, and the importance of the effective implementation of the Agreement.

BBNJ Agreement is a testament to successful diplomacy and international cooperation, and is vital in safeguarding our oceans for future generations.

Panel 1

The BBNJ Agreement and its Contributions to Ocean Governance

Kenneth Wong

Moderator

Senior Director and Senior State Counsel, Attorney-General's Chambers, Singapore

Marie May Jeremie

CEO, Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust

Fred Sarufa

Permanent Representative and Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of Papua New Guinea to the United Nations

Craig Douglas

Deputy Permanent Representative, Permanent Mission of Jamaica to the United Nations

Joanna Mossop

Professor, Victoria University of Wellington

Andreas Aditya Salim

Program Director, Indonesia Ocean Justice Initiative

Key Takeaways

Complementarity and Integration of Existing Area-Based Frameworks: The BBNJ Agreement significantly builds upon pre-existing area-based mechanisms including EBSAs (CBD), PSSAs (IMO), VMEs (FAO), and APEIs (ISA), as well as RFMOs and regional environmental arrangements. While the Agreement shall not undermine the competence of these different IFBs, it nonetheless pushes for greater complementarity and integration. First, the COP may either recommend that such IFBs adopt particular ABMTs, or establish ‘compatible measures’, a term which is still open to interpretation. These compatible measures could effectively corroborate with the relevant IFBs’ ABMTs and, at the same time, bind states that are not parties to the relevant IFBs, but which have ratified the BBNJ Agreement. Second, Parties to the Agreement will be under an obligation to ‘endeavour to promote, as appropriate’, the BBNJ Agreement’s objectives when participating in decision-making under relevant IFBs, which promotes integration of IFBs with the BBNJ Agreement.

Development of More Robust Rules Concerning EIAs: The Agreement maintained that it was the responsibility of States to decide whether planned activities under their jurisdiction with potential environmental impacts could proceed. However, the Agreement also provides for fairly detailed procedures that States must follow, such as screening, post-activity reporting, ensuring transparency,

accountability, and the involvement of relevant stakeholders (e.g., the STB). Speakers also suggested that the BBNJ Agreement and state practice under the Agreement might influence the interpretation of the general EIA obligation found in UNCLOS Article 206.

Effective CBTMT: The implementation of the CBTMT provisions in the Agreement is fundamental for achieving the Agreement’s objectives. The implementation of CBTMT thus necessitates special attention. It was noted that CBTMT efforts should focus on its beneficiaries, considering the specific needs of the States concerned and not duplicating or undermining national efforts.

Operationalisation of the BBNJ Agreement: The operationalisation of the Financial Mechanism was key for the effective implementation of the BBNJ Agreement. Speakers noted that states should ensure that the GEF trust fund and the special fund were reliable sources, instead of relying on the voluntary trust fund. Speakers also highlighted the role of developed states in contributing to these funds. States had to focus on ensuring the Agreement entered into force, and subsequently, envision the processes required to carry out the Agreement’s mandate. In this context, speakers noted that it was crucial to have comprehensive knowledge dissemination and political engagement.

Panel 2

Ratification – Challenges and Opportunities

Robert Beckman

Moderator

Emeritus Professor, CIL-NUS

Maria Angela A. Ponce

**Ambassador and Head of the
Philippines' BBNJ Negotiating Team,
Philippine Department of Foreign
Affairs**

Jeevananth Paliah

**Undersecretary for Strategic Planning
and International Division, Malaysian
Ministry of Natural Resources and
Environmental Sustainability**

John Kemakeza

**Assistant Secretary (Supervising),
Ministry of Foreign Affairs and External
Trade, Solomon Islands Government**

Bingzhuo Li

**Legal Officer, Division for Ocean Affairs
and the Law of the Sea, Office of Legal
Affairs, United Nations**

Key Takeaways

Urgency and Benefits of Early Ratification: Speakers emphasised the importance of swiftly moving towards ratification. Earlier ratification allowed states to shape the initial phases of implementation and decision-making in the Preparatory Commission and the COP, and to benefit from the implementation of the Agreement sooner, including from the equitable sharing of benefits from MGR and DSI, and opportunities for CBTMT. In particular, after 20 September 2025 or the date of entry into force of the Agreement, whichever comes earlier, only States and regional economic integration organisations that have signed or ratified the Agreement will participate in decision-making within the Preparatory Commission. Furthermore, the first meeting of the COP is expected to adopt various key decisions that will lay the foundations for the implementation of the Agreement. Becoming a Party to the Agreement beforehand will ensure full participation in making these decisions. States should seize the current momentum leading up to the Third UN Oceans Conference, which will be held in Nice, France in June 2025, to accelerate progress. Early entry into force would allow for earlier implementation of the Agreement allowing the assistance available under the Agreement for States with limited capacity to be delivered sooner.

Complex Legislative Processes and Stakeholder Engagement: Several countries, such as the Philippines and Malaysia, highlighted complex legislative procedures which required coordination across multiple government agencies and thorough stakeholder consultations.

Speakers discussed the need to adapt existing laws to accommodate the BBNJ Agreement's obligations, and the need for technical expertise and political advocacy to ensure compliance with the BBNJ Agreement.

Capacity Building and Regional Workshops: One key challenge that states face is the lack of capacity. Initiatives like regional capacity-building workshops have been pivotal in preparing states, especially those from developing regions, for participation in BBNJ processes. For example, the Philippines has been actively conducting such workshops, which illustrates proactive international engagement to foster regional readiness to ratify the BBNJ Agreement.

Role of Multi-Sectoral and Multi-Level Coordination: Effective ratification and implementation involve extensive coordination not only within government but also with civil society, academia, and industry. Such comprehensive engagement helps to ensure that the Agreement's objectives are well understood and integrated across sectors that directly impact or benefit from ocean activities.

Political Will and Public Awareness: Speakers underscored the need for strong political will, which must be driven by public awareness and support. Countries were encouraged to enhance public understanding through targeted awareness campaigns, leveraging both the environmental imperatives and economic opportunities presented by the BBNJ Agreement.

Panel 3

Implementation of the BBNJ Agreement

Nguyen Lan-Anh

Moderator

**Associate Professor and Director-General,
East Sea Institute, Diplomatic Academy of
Vietnam**

Fran Humphries

**Associate Professor in Environmental Law,
Griffith University Law School, Australia**

Michael Kanu

**Permanent Representative, Permanent Mission of
the Republic of Sierra Leone to the United
Nations, New York**

Richard Tur de la Concepcion

**First Secretary at the Permanent Mission of
Cuba to the UN, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of
Cuba**

Zeehan Jaafar

**Senior Lecturer, NUS Department of Biological
Sciences**

Nicola Ferri

**Senior Legal and Compliance Adviser, General
Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean of
the FAO**

Torsten Thiele

Founder, Global Ocean Trust

Key Takeaways

Balancing Accelerated Ratification and Effective Implementation: There must be a balance between efforts to accelerate the Agreement's entry into force and the need for its fair and equitable implementation. It was noted that this tension could be a challenge for some states whose legal systems require implementing legislation before ratification can take place. Speakers noted that the functioning of the Agreement and its organs were highly dependent on the sharing of information, which required effective implementation by Parties. In this respect, the role of CBTMT, particularly for developing countries, is fundamental.

Development of National Systems for Compliance with MGR-related Obligations: The BBNJ Agreement stipulates very specific notification obligations before and after MGR collection and after its utilisation, including for commercial purposes. National systems will need to develop domestic regulations and mechanisms to determine how the Party concerned will notify the CHM. In this respect, speakers noted that the Agreement intends for information-sharing to be a live process and that national measures should not unduly block the flow of information.

Moreover, national systems must also ensure compliance with obligations related to the traditional knowledge of IPLC, transparency, and benefit-sharing. Finally, these systems should be designed in view of the actual practices of the scientific community and industry, which, at the end of the day, are obliged to comply with domestic protocols concerning MGR access and benefit-sharing.

Possibilities Involving the Financial Mechanism: The panel discussed the opportunities associated with the financial mechanism if the BBNJ Agreement. It was highlighted that the COP shall decide on how the mechanism will support the Agreement's implementation, including by establishing a Finance Committee to assist it. Speakers suggested that this could be a game-changer for ocean governance. This is because while other funds rely on the commitment from like-minded states to support developing countries, the new special fund allows a wider range of actors, including non-state actors, to support the Agreement's implementation. That said, the COP can direct the funding's destination and only developing countries are eligible for funding. Finally, states that ratify early may benefit from the first-come, first-serve basis of the awarding of grants.

Research Roundtable

Murray Roberts

Moderator

Professor, University of Edinburgh & Founder,
Mara Consultants

Neo Mei Lin

Senior Research Fellow, Tropical Marine
Science Institute, National University of
Singapore, St John's Island National Marine
Laboratory

Ina Tessnow-von Wysocki

Ocean Nexus Postdoctoral Research Fellow,
University of Wollongong

Lucy Harris

PhD Student, University of Southampton and
National Oceanography Centre

Malik Naumann

Research Data Manager, PANGAEA Data
Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science

Laisa Branco

PhD Candidate, The Graduate Institute of
International and Development Studies

David Vousden

Honorary Professor of Ocean Governance,
Rhodes University; Chief Technical Advisor,
UNDP GEF Sargasso Sea Project

Key Takeaways

Integration of Traditional and Scientific Knowledge:

Researchers emphasised the importance of integrating scientific data with traditional knowledge from IPLC to better understand marine biodiversity and inform conservation. Such integration aids in the accurate identification of species distribution and human activities.

Data Management and FAIR Principles: It is crucial to ensure that MGR data and metadata adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. A standardised approach to metadata and high-quality data repositories would enhance the transparency and utility of data, facilitating its use in compliance with the Agreement and supporting broader scientific research.

Precautionary and Ecosystem Approaches: The BBNJ Agreement's focus on the precautionary and ecosystem approaches ensures that state parties' actions are based on sufficient scientific evidence rather than waiting for complete certainty. These approaches could expedite protective measures and sustainable management practices for marine biodiversity.

The panel discussion reflected on intergenerational equity and considered the rights of nature. The actions required include governmental decisions on marine resource management and the implementation of conservation strategies informed by the latest scientific findings.

Connectivity: States and the scientific community need to actively recognise and address various types of connectivity of ABNJ to broader ecosystems and coastal areas (linear, circular, ecosystem, etc.) to further develop and effectively implement the Agreement.

Costs and Institutional Design Efficiencies: The roundtable noted the importance of considering the transaction costs associated with data management and the overall implementation of the Agreement. Efficient institutional designs can reduce these costs, facilitating smoother implementation and better utilisation of marine genetic resources. For example, reference could be taken from the Sargasso Sea Commission's development of a Socio-Ecosystem Diagnostic Analysis which informed its Strategic Action Plan for ecosystem management in ABNJ.

Fireside Chat

Co-Chairs of the BBNJ Preparatory Commission

Rena Lee

Moderator

**Singapore Ambassador for
International Law**

Adam McCarthy

**Chief Counsel and First Assistant
Secretary, Department of Foreign Affairs
and Trade, Australia**

Janine Felson

**Deputy Permanent Representative,
Permanent Mission of Belize to the
United Nations**

Key Takeaways

Ratification and Entry into Force: While it was important to obtain 60 ratifications so that the BBNJ Agreement could enter into force, the end-goal was for the Agreement to achieve universality and well exceed 60 ratifications.

Ensuring Progress: The co-chairs explained that the agenda for the BBNJ Preparatory Commission covered a wide range of issues prior to the first BBNJ Conference of Parties (COP1) and ahead of the BBNJ Agreement's entry into force. Elaborating on the first Preparatory Commission meeting to be held in April 2025, the co-chairs said that delegations should be prepared to state their national positions and views on the proposals put forth in the Preparatory Commission's official documents. Delegations should exercise flexibility so that compromises could be made in the lead up to the Agreement's entry into force.

Inclusive and Transparent Process: The co-chairs emphasised the need for inclusivity, meaningful participation, and transparency throughout the proceedings. The Preparatory Commission had to balance the need to get through the voluminous, technical and novel work laid out in its agenda, and allowing parties to participate in discussions. Different stakeholders should be consulted. For example, the scientific community, NGOs and academia could offer their expertise to the Preparatory Commission. The co-chairs said that if States provided the mandate, intersessional or working group meetings could be convened to involve non-State

expertise.

Holistic Focus on the Different Aspects of the BBNJ Agreement: The co-chairs highlighted the need for discussions on all four aspects of the BBNJ Agreement – MGRs, ABMTs, EIAs, and CB&TMT – to advance during the Preparatory Commission meetings. States should adopt the view that they had interests in all pillars, instead of focussing merely on individual issues. Delegates should focus on the interactions between the different aspects of the BBNJ Agreement. For example, all four aspects were linked to the BBNJ CHM.

Implementation of the BBNJ Agreement: The Preparatory Commission's outcomes were aimed to ensure the smooth implementation of the BBNJ Agreement. For example, financial rules were dependent on the BBNJ Secretariat arrangements, in particular whether the Secretariat would be an independent entity or linked to the UN. Issues around monitoring and surveillance in ABNJ could only be tackled after more fundamental questions, such as the size and function of subsidiary bodies, were decided. The co-chairs encouraged delegations to think about how the BBNJ Agreement could be future-proofed. Additionally, States should think through concrete proposals for the treaty regime that could be presented to the COP at the end of the Preparatory Commission process. It was crucial for states to achieve a clear collective understanding of the direction and practical steps necessary for the Agreement's implementation.

Panel 4

Cooperation with Relevant Instruments, Frameworks and Bodies (IFBs) under the BBNJ Agreement

Zhen Sun

Moderator

**Associate Professor
(Research/OSGM), World Maritime
University**

René Lefeber

**Legal Adviser & Head of the
International Law Division, Ministry of
Foreign Affairs of the Kingdom of the
Netherlands**

Youna Lyons

**Chair, Advisory Committee on Protection
of the Sea (ACOPS)**

David Freestone

**Executive Secretary, Sargasso Sea
Commission**

Nichola Clark

Senior Officer, Pew Charitable Trusts

Viktoria Varga Lencses

**Senior Fishery Officer, Food and
Agriculture Organization**

Key Takeaways

Promoting Cooperation and Coordination: The BBNJ Agreement includes the obligation to not undermine the mandate of relevant IFBs (Article 5(2)), and an obligation to promote the objectives of the BBNJ Agreement in relevant IFBs (Article 8(2)). This should be seen as an opportunity for constructive engagement, promoting a more integrated governance approach to tackle increasing pressure from human activities and global challenges. Such an opportunity comes with challenges. Speakers agreed that it remained to be seen how relevant IFBs would interact with BBNJ processes in practice.

Varied Profile of Engaging Relevant IFBs that the BBNJ Process can Benefit from and Vice-Versa: Panelists discussed existing examples of relevant IFBs involved in activities in ABNJ, lessons learned and progress made when seeking to develop international cooperation mechanisms. Examples included institutional mechanisms developed to protect the marine environment of the Sargasso Sea (e.g. through the Hamilton Declaration and establishment of the Sargasso Sea Commission and its accreditation as an observer to a number of IFBs competent in this sea area), as well as institutional and regional fisheries regulatory frameworks (e.g. developed under the auspices of the FAO and different RFMOs). Panelists also envisaged the possibility for the BBNJ processes to recognise ABMTs adopted under relevant IFBs, thereby potentially enlarging the reach of their recognition, eventually to global recognition.

Entry Points into Processes under the BBNJ Agreement: Noting the absence of a definition of IFBs, the panelists emphasised the numerous entry points provided in the Agreement for involvement of the IFBs, including through the COP and the work of subsidiary bodies to inter alia contribute relevant knowledge and expertise. Panelists highlighted the proposal of ABMTs to the COP, regular consultations to enhance cooperation and coordination with and among relevant IFBs, and the invitation

to IFBs to share reports with the COP on measures they have adopted towards the BBNJ Agreement's objectives. The panel also noted that entry points differed in different subject areas under the BBNJ Agreement. Whereas the establishment of ABMTs is a COP-driven process, the EIA processes privilege state-driven procedures. For COP-driven ABMT processes, the implementation of the obligation to not undermine appears to be closely aligned with ensuring that these processes include (i.e. consult and cooperate with) other relevant IFBs. For EIA state-driven processes, the BBNJ Agreement exempts states from the obligations to conduct screening and/or scoping under the provisions where the planned activity being considered has already been the subject of an equivalent assessment in accordance with another IFB. Panelists envisaged that instances where states unduly resorted to such exemptions could be brought to the attention of the Implementation and Compliance Committee. Finally, several practical considerations for the promotion of the Agreement's objectives in other IFBs were brought up, such as the role of BBNJ Parties that are also parties to the IFB and the BBNJ Secretariat (e.g., as an observer in other IFBs)

Challenges in Implementing the Obligation to Not Undermine: A good faith interpretation of the Agreement would favour international cooperation and coordination and focuses on complementarity. For that, the interpretation of the compatibility provisions (i.e. in the context of ABMTs) is essential. Furthermore, a representational challenge was noted through the example of Regional Fishery Bodies as relevant IFBs. There is no existing and highly relevant State practice that could be drawn upon to model the participation of RFMOs in the processes of the BBNJ Agreement. In the context of the EIA process, the assessment of 'equivalence' would require similar considerations. Panelists highlighted the critical need for the many guidelines to be developed by the first COP to clarify the way these challenges will be handled, with respect to both compatible ABMTs and equivalent EIAs.

Panel 5

Subsidiary Bodies

Nilufer Oral
Moderator
Director, NUS CIL

Júlia Schütz Veiga
Visiting researcher, The Nippon
Foundation - University of Edinburgh
Ocean Voices Programme

Bupe Mwambingu
Biodiversity Partnerships Manager,
Basecamp Research, UK

Kim Wonhee
Director of Ocean Law Research
Department, Korea Institute of Ocean
Science and Technology

Marie Antonette Juinio-Meñez
Professor, Marine Science Institute,
University of the Philippines

Kahlil Hassanali
Senior Research Officer, Institute of
Marine Affairs, Trinidad and Tobago

Key Takeaways

The CBTMT Committee: The speakers emphasised that, while distinct, capacity-building and technology transfer are interconnected and essential to the success of the Agreement. The CBTMT Committee should be tasked with distinguishing these concepts to develop strategies that strengthen capacity-building efforts and, in particular, ensure effective and sustainable technology transfer. This process should be guided by the needs and priorities identified by states, promoting equitable access to resources and their utilisation, as well as associated knowledge. A key aspect of this effort is understanding specific national contexts while fostering the broad sharing of marine technology and operational practices.

Function, Composition, and Procedure of the STB: The STB plays a crucial role in integrating scientific knowledge into the Agreement's decision-making processes, especially those concerning ABMTs and EIAs. Given that the ocean is a socio-ecological system, the STB should include experts from diverse areas beyond the natural sciences, such as the social sciences and law. The speakers also addressed the number of members in the STB, which the Agreement is silent on. Using the experience of the ISA Legal and Technical Commission (LTC) as an example, it was suggested that four seats for each regional group and a few others for IPLC might strike a reasonable balance, totalling around 25 to 26 members. Finally, while the STB Rules of Procedure have yet to be adopted, the Agreement determines that the STB meetings shall be open to observers and that its activities must be transparently conducted unless otherwise decided by the COP.

Effectiveness and Inclusivity in the ABS Committee: The ABS Committee will play a fundamental role in enabling the

use of MGRs in a fair and equitable manner. To this end, speakers suggested that the ABS Committee should focus on four key areas: governance, capacity-building, transparency, and integrity. The Committee will be tasked with defining rules for ABS, particularly regarding the DSI and beyond physical samples. These can take the form, for example, of fair access protocols and guidance on the establishment of standard monitoring mechanisms. Capacity building is crucial to the effective implementation of such protocols and guidance. Governance over MGRs will also be enhanced through greater data transparency, such as through the ABS Committee's activities and private and public databases. Finally, ethical integrity should guide the implementation of standards and guidelines by states and relevant stakeholders.

A Unique Model for the Finance Committee: The Agreement did not define the model for the Finance Committee, and instead left it to be established by the COP. Speakers noted that the Finance Committee will be unique as compared to existing models (e.g., for the ISA, the UNFCCC, and the CBD), as it will be able to make recommendations to the COP on the use of the Financial Mechanism in supporting the BBNJ bureaucracy and CBTMT efforts.

The ICC: Speakers described the ICC as the cornerstone for the successful implementation of the Agreement. Despite the Agreement's brevity on the operation of the ICC, it is crucial that the ICC is effective in ensuring compliance with the Agreement's provisions. The ICC needs to be designed and empowered to not only oversee compliance but also to facilitate effective and coherent implementation across different jurisdictions. To this end, speakers suggested that transparency in the ICC is key.

Panel 6

Clearing House Mechanism (CHM)

Wendy Yap

Moderator

Director (International Biodiversity Conservation), National Parks Board Singapore

Thembile Joyini

Judge of the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS)

Arvin Diesmos

Director, Biodiversity Knowledge Management Department, ASEAN Centre for Biodiversity

Mahesh Pradhan

UNEP COBSEA Coordinator (United Nations Environment Programme; Coordinating Body for the Seas of East Asia)

Lowri Griffiths

Head of the Ocean Policy Unit, UK Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office

Thomas Vanagt

Co-CEO, 3BIO

Thamasak Yeemin

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, Ramkhamhaeng University, Huamark, Bangkok, Thailand

Key Takeaways

Centrality of the CHM in the BBNJ Agreement: The speakers agreed that the CHM is fundamental for the implementation of the Agreement. Of note, the CHM is mentioned 39 times throughout the treaty text. The CHM serves as a publicly accessible repository for states' information-related obligations and also an instrument supporting the activities and decision-making processes of states and BBNJ subsidiary bodies. It plays a crucial role in industry players' due diligence processes, which will be a part of their compliance with relevant standards and guidelines.

Accessibility and Simplicity: The CHM should be user-friendly and straightforward to navigate, ensuring simplicity in its design to serve a wide array of stakeholders effectively. Speakers suggested that the CHM should not aim at comprehensiveness per se but instead aim to be functional in the implementation of the Agreement. A focus on comprehensiveness could lead to, among others, a more complex interface, delays in the implementation of the BBNJ Agreement's obligations, and a risk of duplication of existing

public databases, such as the Ocean Biogeographic Information System.

The BBNJ CHM as a Marine Biodiversity Knowledge-Sharing Hub: On the other hand, other speakers said that the BBNJ CHM should consider playing the role of a 'knowledge-sharing hub', such as the UNFCCC CHM. Some speakers opined that the BBNJ CHM should recognise the potential role of regional biodiversity centres.

Effective Management System and Capacity-Building: The success of the CHM hinges upon an effective data management system that may be operated by all relevant stakeholders, including developing countries and IPLC. Speakers underlined the importance of the early implementation of a batch identifier system, efficient and harmonised metadata standards, and compliance with the FAIR principles. Speakers also emphasised that capacity-building was crucial to ensure that the data management system operated effectively.

The BBNJ Symposium 2025 was concluded by Dr Nilufer Oral, Director of the CILNUS, who celebrated the event's conclusion as the culmination of extensive preparations and a long-held vision. Dr Oral also highlighted the decades-long journey from the initial conceptualisation to the anticipated implementation of the BBNJ Agreement. Reflecting on significant historical milestones, such as crucial workshops and conferences in the lead up to the BBNJ Agreement, Dr Oral acknowledged the vital contributions of various individuals and organisations, notably Ambassador-at-Large Professor Tommy Koh and Ambassador for International Law Rena Lee.

Dr Oral extended gratitude to all panellists, speakers, rapporteurs, and participants for their expertise and dedication, which contributed to the event's success. Dr Oral described the BBNJ Agreement as a symbol of international unity for the common good, as it aimed at the protection and sustainable management of marine resources. She also expressed optimism for the future implementation of the BBNJ Agreement and invited continued engagement and collaboration to advance international ocean governance.

The two-day Symposium was attended by over 250 participants in person, with an additional 200+ following the discussions online. Approximately 80 in-person and 100 online delegates attended seven satellite events on 20 February 2025.

The participants at the Symposium represented more than 70 countries, with the approximate geographic breakdown as follows:

- Asia: 32% (Singapore, China, India, Malaysia, Japan, others)
- Europe: 30% (United Kingdom, Germany, Netherlands, Italy, France, others)
- North America: 22% (United States, Canada)
- Oceania: 7% (Australia, New Zealand, others)
- Africa: 5% (South Africa, Nigeria, Kenya, others)
- Latin American and the Caribbean: 4% (Brazil, Argentina, Chile, others)

Approximately 20% of participants represented Small Island Developing States, while all 10 ASEAN Member States were represented.

Approximately 50% of the delegates represented academic institutions, 30% were government officials, 10% were affiliated with NGOs, and another 10% were from industry and other sectors (including consultants, Intergovernmental Organisation (IGOs), legal practitioners).

Approximately 9% of participants were students and PhD researchers.

Snapshots from the Symposium

Meeting report was prepared by Dr. Anna Gebruk, Eduardo Cavalcanti de Mello Filho, and Digvijay Sanjay Rewatkar on 3 April 2025 based on the minutes prepared by the Symposium rapporteurs:

- Amelia Westmoreland, PhD candidate, HOTBIO network
- Catherine Brown, Marine Socio-Ecological Researcher
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- Jason Cleland, Research Assistant, University of Edinburgh & Mara Consultants
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- Dr Su Wai Mon, Research Fellow, CIL-NUS
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The present version 1.1 was finalised on 15 April 2025 following revisions by CIL-NUS, MFA Singapore, and the Symposium speakers.

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